

Ethical AI for Mental Health Contexts: A Focus on Conservative Communities and Annie the Chatbot

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Abstract This paper examines ethical protocols in the development of ‘Annie’: a therapeutic generative AI chatbot for supporting anxiety and depression in conservative communities. Annie is an empathetic chatbot that utilises advanced natural language processing techniques for accurate emotion detection and response generation. Moreover, Annie is culturally aware and religiously sensitive. A key element in the development of Annie the chatbot is a thorough ethical framework to ensure the safety of patients and practitioners, and wider organisations and stakeholders, within the specific context of the conservative communities it is aimed at. Initial consultations and workshops with mental health experts from Qatar and Saudi Arabia support the design elements of Annie the chatbot, and research is ongoing to produce an ethical framework that can be used as a reference in the development of AI tools for mental health. Therefore, this paper considers some of the key aspects of responsible and ethical AI based chatbots to ensure ‘harmless, helpful and honest’ design and implementation as the gold standard.

Keywords: AI, Mental Health, Ethics, Chatbot

1 Responsible and Ethical AI for Mental Health

1.1 The Importance of Ethics in the Development of AI Chatbots

The first natural language processing (NLP) computer program, named ELIZA, simulated the therapy developed by the psychologist Carl Rogers. Its designer, Weizenbaum, aimed to show that ‘communication between man and machine was superficial’ (Epstein and Klinkenberg 2017); however, his assistant, started to form a relationship with the program and disclosed personal information to it, despite being aware of its purpose. Therefore, Weizenbaum warned that human engagement with technology may not be fully rational, and the ‘ELIZA effect’ came to be used to describe people’s tendency to ascribe human traits to computers. ELIZA was a very basic NLP compared to today’s AI technology, highlighting the need for strict ethical principles to prevent harm to patients. Therefore, this ongoing research involves the development and evaluation of an ethical framework that considers how advances in technology are making it possible for users to converse with a chatbot as if it is actually a real person. While Coghlan et al (2023) claim that chatbots are not able to respond based on empathy or provide tailored responses, this is changing, as designs are becoming increasingly sophisticated.

The design of an effective and safe chatbot must consider factors such as patient and practitioner trust, and crucially, safety (Parker et al 2018). It must not cause emotional harm and it needs to be ensured that it will not misunderstand what the user is saying.

Importantly, the chatbot should include a safety mechanism whereby at risk patients are signposted or referred to a medical practitioner, as failure to do so can have devastating consequences. Despite these challenges, chatbots have many advantages, not least, patient's preference for privacy where stigmatisation exists, as well as their ease of accessibility (Coghlan et al 2023). In addition, during the design process, access to the chatbot and confidentiality must be carefully decided on to prevent data breaches, including how chats are logged and whether practitioners can access to what has been said. While the consequences of failing to ensure an AI chatbot is ethical can be disastrous for patients, they can also harm the reputation of the designer, the owner, and the organisation using the said chatbot.

1.2 Annie the Chatbot and Developing a Responsible and Ethical Framework

Annie is a the therapeutic chatbot for supporting anxiety and depression. It is culturally sensitive and involves an empathetic therapeutic algorithm to support the implementation of an API, base model specialised therapeutic AI tool. Ethics are at the core of the design of Annie the chatbot, and the aim is to develop a 'helpful, honest, and harmless' therapeutic chatbot that is culturally aware and religiously sensitive. Annie has two pathways: firstly, practitioner facing functionality to allow the setting up of profiles for patients and summarise the patient's condition and its severity; secondly, patient facing functionality for diagnosis, risk assessment, therapy plans and their activation, and signposting. A unique aspect of Annie the chatbot is that it is targeted at conservative communities -a context that requires specific elements of ethical protocols to be considered.

To develop a robust ethical framework for AI in mental healthcare, including to inform the design of Annie the chatbot, a mixed methods research approach is being used, which involves workshops and interviews with mental health professionals, patients, ethicists, and AI technologists. This inclusive approach will ensure the framework under development reflects a wide range of perspectives and addresses the needs of various parties. Based on the data collected, an ethical framework will be designed, which will utilise an iterative process through gaining feedback and carrying out pilot testing in real-world mental health facilities in order to refine the framework based on its practical application. This will foster trust in the use of AI within mental health, as well as ensuring safety.

2 Ethics in the Context of Conservative Communities

Confidentiality and anonymity is a major ethical concern for patients and clinical practices alike. Failure to ensure privacy can present risks, and these risks may be more concerning in the context of societies where there is stigma and shame around mental health, as patients are likely to be even more concerned about disclosure of their condition. While an AI chatbot may support the patient's privacy in regard to accessing support, which is useful in the context of conservative communities, practitioner involvement is still essential to monitor the condition of the patient and intervene when necessary. Therefore, an AI chatbot should provide a kind of alliance with human therapists. This is the approach favoured by mental health therapists and experts consulted

so far in the conservative communities of Qatar and Saudi Arabia. While every effort should be made to develop an AI chatbot that displays empathy, the emotions of the patient must be considered, and practitioners must make patients aware that they are not speaking to a person; failure to do so could potentially cause distress to the patient, especially if they are unable to converse with friends and family due to the stigma and shame around mental health. Ensuring an AI chatbot provides a safe and evidence based option is essential (van der Schyff et al 2023). Moreover, mental health sufferers are more vulnerable than the general population and must not be exposed to the dangers of inappropriate advice. Even so, where mental health services are difficult to access, whether because of shortages, or stigma and shame, the benefits of an AI chatbot may outweigh the risk of harm.

Patient choice and equity is an essential part of medical ethics, and in conservative communities, approaches to mental health should be tailored to need. An example of this is indigenous psychologies (Haque 2018), such as Islamic psychology, which can help to provide more appropriate support than more common Western models. In this way, the patient has a level of autonomy over their treatment and is more likely to follow the advice given by the AI chatbot, as it will be both culturally acceptable and familiar. Eubanks (2018) explains that some AI applications are biased and discriminate against certain groups, therefore as well as considering culturally relevant treatment options, patients' values and norms should be embedded during the development stage of the AI chatbot to ensure accurate assumptions and appropriate responses.

While the ethical considerations herein are by no means exhaustive, they highlight some of the key issues involved in developing responsible and ethical AI chatbots. The current research and development of Annie the chatbot is helping to ensure that ethical procedures in AI keep up with the rapid pace and make ultimate use of this technology.

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